

Does building more energy efficient homes in Brazil imply increasing CO2 emissions?

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Executive Summary

This report explores the potential impact of improving energy efficiency in low-income housing in Brazil through the reduction of U-values in building envelopes. The study utilizes Supply and Use Tables (SUTs) to evaluate CO₂ emissions associated with replacing masonry (brick-and-mortar) walls with steel frame systems, known for being almost 6 times more thermally insulating. Energy consumption for both alternatives was calculated for a 42-m² standalone house using Energy Plus. The results indicate that although new materials lead to approximately a 1.33% increase in CO₂ emissions, this rise is compensated by reductions in CO₂ emissions from the electricity sector within a 5-year timeframe. The sustained decrease in energy consumption from the new envelope system has the potential to save over 3.5 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions over 30 years. The innovative use of SUTs in this study provides a comprehensive understanding of the entire economic chain linked to the proposed scenarios. The report concludes by emphasizing the significance of exploring strategies aimed at reducing the energy demand in Latin America and the Caribbean.

1 Introduction

People living in thermally uncomfortable houses may experience health and productivity issues. Low-income families are particularly vulnerable to these problems and often allocate a higher percentage of their income to energy bills for heating and cooling, contributing to the phenomenon known as "fuel poverty."

Energy efficiency is a measure of how effectively a building can maintain a comfortable indoor environment with minimal energy consumption. One of the primary factors influencing a house's energy efficiency is its building envelope (Sadineni, et al., 2011; Ferrara, et al., 2017) — the physical barrier that separates the indoor and outdoor environments, including walls, roofs, windows, and doors. The thermal properties of the envelope (e.g., thermal conductivity, thermal transmissivity/U-value, density, specific heat, latent heat) impact the heat transfer between the house and its surroundings (Mendes, et al., 2022). A well-designed envelope can minimize heat loss in winter and heat gain in summer, maintaining a stable and comfortable indoor temperature. This configuration reduces the energy required for indoor conditioning, thereby improving the building's energy efficiency.

The reduced energy demand of a well-insulated building not only enhances the well-being of its occupants but also lowers its CO₂ emissions. However, it's worth noting that the production of better-insulating building materials can sometimes result in higher CO₂ emissions during the construction phase (Lin, et al., 2021; Zhu, et al., 2013).

Life cycle analysis (LCA) is commonly used to compare the environmental impacts of building materials. Specific data sources provide information on material flow, energy use, and CO₂ emissions throughout their production, transportation, installation, maintenance, and end-of-life treatment (Science Direct Topics, 2024). However, the system boundaries of an LCA analysis typically focus on the key processes related to material production, transportation, and use.

Conversely, supply and use tables (SUTs) are an economic accounting framework offering a comprehensive overview of goods and services flows in an economy over a specific period (OECD, 2022). They capture the production, distribution, and use of goods and services, providing insights into the interrelationships between different sectors of the economy and the final uses of goods and services (OECD, 2022). In this regard, SUTs offer a broader perspective on how changes in the construction sector influence the overall economy and CO₂ emissions of a country.

Therefore, using SUTs, this project addresses the question: "If Brazil implements policies to reduce the U-values of envelopes in its low-income housing stock, with the goal of decreasing energy consumption for indoor conditioning, what will be the impacts in terms of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions?"

2 Methodology

Figure 1 presents an overview of the methodology. The full parameters regarding the energy simulation of the low-income house; the material flows used for each scenario; and the calculation of the electricity consumption reduction can be found on the Appendices. The modeling of the SUTs was performed using MARIO (Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output), a python package developed by Department of Energy of Politecnico di Milano (Tahavori, et al., 2023).

The 3 scenarios evaluated in the present work are:

- Scenario 1 (baseline): 100% Conventional Construction
- Scenario 2 (new materials): 96.45% Conventional Construction + 3.55% New construction (where this 3.55% market share represents the low-income houses with the new construction system)
- Scenario 3 (energy reduction): Electricity from households reduced by 0.92% (the national savings calculated using energy simulations of a low-income household).

Table 1 presents the layers in the conventional construction system (structural masonry) and the new construction system. For this project, we defined the insulating envelope (walls) as comprising steel frame structure + plasterboard or cement board + glass wool insulation. One can notice that the U-values of the walls decreased by approximately 84%. The remaining parts of the envelope (roof, floor, windows, and doors) were not altered.

Figure 1 – Overview of the methodology.

Table 1 – Conventional and new construction systems evaluated.

		Wall layers	Thick-ness (m)	Thermal conduct. (W/m.K)	Density (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat (J/kg.K)	U-value (W/m ² .K)	Thermal Capacity (kJ/m ² .K)
Conventional Constr. System	Internal and external walls	Coating mortar	0.020	1.15	1950	1000	5.23	210.4
		Concrete Block	0.140	0.905	1166.1	810.9		
		Coating mortar	0.020	1.15	1950	1000		
New Constr. System	External walls	Cement board	0.010	0.128	1618	830	0.82	24.5
		Glasswool	0.050	0.045	55	700		
		Plasterboard	0.0125	0.35	875	840		
	Internal walls	Plasterboard	0.0125	0.35	875	840	0.85	20.3
		Glasswool	0.050	0.045	55	700		
		Plasterboard	0.0125	0.35	875	840		

Figure 2 displays the simulated 42-m² standalone housing unit featured in this study, which represents an actual model from the MCMV stock. Although the MCMV program encompasses apartment blocks and some 3-bedroom options, all units constructed in 2011 were modeled after this standalone unit due to time constraints. The complete parameters used for the energy simulation can be found in Appendix I. To accommodate the diverse climates of the country, the houses were simulated in 5 out of the 8 Brazilian Bioclimatic Zones (BZ). The electricity savings resulting from the new envelope system ranged from 0% to 21.3%, depending on the BZ.

Appendix I also outlines the calculations performed to estimate the overall reduction in the country's electricity consumption. In the absence of official data, we assumed that the number of houses built in each Brazilian state was proportional to its population. The national reduction of 5.4% was derived from the average savings in each BZ, weighted by the number of units in the predominant BZ of each state.

Figure 2 – Floor plan, section and 3D model of the standalone low-income housing unit simulated on Energy Plus

Table 2 presents the variations in the commodities computed on scenario 2 (new materials). They refer to the subtraction of the materials related to the construction of 20.3 million m² of external walls and 14.8 million m² of internal walls (from 289.6 thousand housing units with 42m² floor plan each). Considering the costs/m² of floor plan with the different systems - R\$ 936.95 (€402.64) for the masonry walls¹ and R\$ 1,405.42 (€603.96) for the steel frame walls² – the low-income housing stock corresponded to 3.55% of the market share of the Construction activity in 2011 in Brazil. The calculations and assumptions behind these values are detailed in Appendix II.

Table 2 – Alterations in the commodities carried out on scenario 2 (new materials)

Modified Commodity¹ (EXIOBASE HYBRID v3 – 2011)	Convent. Construction² (Tonnes) (96.45% market share)	New Construction³ (Tonnes) (3.55% market share)
Cement; lime and plaster	-1,436,085.40	+461,364.50
Sand and clay	-5,737,949.90	+144.1
Stone	-3,551,199.80	+75,369.00
Gas/Diesel Oil	-1,896.30	-
Liquefied Petroleum Gases (LPG)	-1,672.50	-
Natural gas and services related to natural gas extraction; excluding surveying	-194	-
Basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys and first products thereof	-18,244.80	+502,968.20
Other non-ferrous metal ores and concentrates	-	+99.4
Aluminium ores and concentrates	-	+96.3
Iron ores	-	+63.8
Chemical and fertilizer minerals; salt and other mining and quarrying products n.e.c.	-	+204,794.00
Glass and glass products	-	+2.5
Plastics; basic	-	+1,219.40
Paper and paper products	-	+1,261.60
Secondary paper for treatment; Re-processing of secondary paper into new pulp	-	+18,978.20

¹ Note: Commodities whose quantities varied by less than 1 tonne were not altered.

² This activity encompassed the rest of the conventional construction sector. The commodities related to the construction of masonry walls of the low-income houses were subtracted.

³ This activity encompassed the construction of steel frame walls in the low-income houses.

¹ From with the average cost/m² tables published by Brazilian Civil Construction Union (Sinduscon).

² From interviews with budgeting professionals.

3 Results

Scenario	CO2 emissions by unit of output of “construction work” commodity ¹ (f)	Total CO2 emissions from the “construction work” commodity ² (F)	Total CO2 emissions from the electricity-related commodities ³ (F)
1 (Baseline)	241.00 tonne _{CO2} /MEuro	44449772.8 tonne _{CO2}	12913011.6 tonne _{CO2}
2 (New Materials)	244.2 (+1.33%) tonne _{CO2} /MEuro	45043326.5 (+1.33%) tonne _{CO2}	-
3 (Energy Reduction)	-	-	12794280.7 (-0.93%) tonne _{CO2}

¹This value represents the CO2 emissions from the entire Brazilian economic chain related to the production of 1MEuro of construction work in 2011 - all direct commodities required for the activity, the indirect commodities required to produce these direct commodities and so on (from the entire world).

²This value represents the total CO2 emissions from the entire Brazilian economic chain related to the production construction work in 2011 (in case of scenario 1 and 3, M€204,480; scenario 2 - M€206,929, due to the slight increase in construction costs for the new envelope) (from the entire world).

³This value represents the total CO2 emissions from the entire Brazilian economic chain of the energy-related commodities in 2011 (Electricity by biomass and waste, by coal, by gas, by Geothermal, by hydro, by nuclear, by petroleum and other oil derivatives, by solar photovoltaic, by solar thermal, by tide; wave; ocean, and by wind).

The difference in global CO2 emissions between scenario 2 (new materials) and scenario 1 (baseline) amounted to approximately 594 thousand tonne_{CO2}. This difference was mainly due to the increased consumption of steel, which, in turn, requires various other commodities. Even though the new envelope system significantly reduced the demand for cement, a major contributor to global CO2 emissions, this reduction was not enough to offset the increase in CO2 emissions associated with the production of steel, gypsum and the other materials in the new envelope.

In contrast, the decrease in CO2 emissions between scenario 3 (energy reduction) and scenario 1 (baseline) was 119 thousand tonne_{CO2}, summing up all energy sources. Since the reduction in energy consumption was uniformly applied across all sources, the impacts on the energy commodities were mitigated by the same proportion. However, in a more realistic Brazilian scenario, coal and gas power plants would be deactivated first, further diminishing CO2 emissions. At the present rate, the reduction in CO2 emissions due to energy reduction would offset the increased CO2 emissions from the new construction system within 5 years.

Over the next 30 years, assuming unchanged economic, environmental, and technical circumstances for illustrative purposes, the savings in CO2 emissions resulting from reduced electricity consumption would accumulate to 3.6 million tonne_{CO2}. This improved performance would persist indefinitely, alleviating the financial burden on low-income families and enhancing their overall well-being.

4 Discussion

In contrast to conventional LCA analyses that typically focus on CO2 emissions directly associated with the lifecycle of the selected materials, this project employed SUTs to

offer a holistic perspective on the environmental impacts of transitioning low-income building sector envelope materials. By utilizing this comprehensive economic analysis tool, we were able to assess not only the direct emissions per square meter of walls but also understand the broader implications for the entire Brazilian economy. The advantage of SUTs lies in their ability to reveal the interconnectedness of economic activities, providing a 'whole picture' view. This approach allowed us to quantify the total Brazilian CO₂ emissions arising from the alteration of construction materials, considering the ripple effects throughout the supply chain. The same can be said for the reduction on electricity consumption.

Due to time constraints in this project, several assumptions were made for efficiency. The modeling focused solely on low-income residential units constructed in 2011, considering them exclusively as standalone units of the smallest possible layout. Besides the fact that these 289.6 thousand homes represent only 5% of the total number of houses built since the start of the “Minha Casa Minha Vida” social program (5.8 million), this oversimplification neglected the presence of apartment buildings and variations in floor area. Additionally, energy efficiency improvements were limited to walls, excluding potential enhancements for windows, doors, and roofs. A uniform construction system was applied across all bioclimatic zones, overlooking the study of climate-appropriate systems that could further enhance energy savings. These assumptions, while expedient, underestimate the actual potential for reducing electricity consumption and CO₂ emissions of the Brazilian housing sector. A more comprehensive and realistic approach could unveil even greater positive impacts.

According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), emissions from buildings represent one-third of the total reductions required to align with the IEA’s Sustainable Development Scenario (GlobalABC/IEA/UNEP, 2020). As outlined in the report, to counteract the expansion of floor space and the rise in energy-consuming services, such as indoor conditioning, the global average building energy intensity per unit of floor area must be reduced by at least 30% by 2050 (GlobalABC/IEA/UNEP, 2020). In this sense, the present project is in line with the IEA’s roadmap for new buildings, advocating adopting for the adoption of decarbonization strategies, enforcement of mandatory building energy codes, and the promotion of high energy performance.

For future research, some topics that can be explored are:

- Improve the low-income housing data (including the different housing layouts and their actual distribution per state).
- Carry out more energy simulations considering more suitable construction materials for each state and the different housing layouts available.
- Consider heating energy consumption in the colder regions.
- Evaluate potential influence the average and peak temperature increases on Heating, Ventilating and Air Conditioning (HVAC) savings due to climate change.
- Expand the analysis for the whole MCMV project (5.8 million houses up to 2023).
- Check financial impacts of the implementation of the new (more expensive) construction system on construction companies.
- Check impact on jobs and secondary industries.

5 Conclusion

The model yielded positive results: despite a 1.33% increase in CO₂ emissions for the Brazilian economy when using the new, more insulating construction materials, these additional emissions will be offset by the reduction in CO₂ emissions from the electricity sector within 5 years. The permanent reduction in energy consumption with the new envelope system has the potential to exceed 3.5 million tonnes of CO₂ over 30 years. This enhanced energy efficiency not only lowers electricity bills but also enhances the well-being of occupants through the building's entire lifecycle.

Given the simplifications and assumptions made in this study, the results are conservative. The potential reductions in CO₂ emissions could be significantly higher when considering factors such as the optimal construction system for each region, accurate numbers for the MCMV low-income housing stock, the more diverse building layouts in the program, and the impact of rising temperatures across Brazil due to climate change.

The utilization of SUTs in this comparative study is a novel approach that has proven successful. SUTs offer a holistic view of the entire economic chain related to the proposed scenarios, providing crucial insights for informed decision-making.

In terms of policy insights, in alignment with the IEA's objectives for the building sector, the current findings suggest that transitioning to renewable energy sources is crucial in the Latin American and Caribbean region. However, there remains ample opportunity to explore scenarios in which the electricity would not need to be produced in the first place. This can be accomplished through the implementation of more stringent building regulations aimed at enhancing the thermal performance and energy efficiency of the new and existing building stock.

6 References

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7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix I - Modelling of the low-income houses

Table 3 presents the parameters adopted to estimate the annual energy consumption for indoor conditioning (thermal load) of the model house with the different construction systems. The energy simulation was carried out in the Energy Plus software, version 9.6. These parameters align with the guidelines outlined in the Brazilian performance standard for residential buildings, ABNT NBR 15575. To better reflect the Brazilian context, the simulation assumes that houses are equipped solely with air conditioning, activated when the temperatures in the primary living spaces (the living room and bedrooms) exceed 25°C. This table follows the best practices from Mendes et al. (2024).

Table 3 - Simulation parameters used in the Energy Plus software.

Internal heat gains			
<i>Lighting system</i>			
Installed capacity density	5 W/m ²	Occupancy pattern	
Radiant fraction	0.32	Bedrooms	6h-8h and 22h-00h
Visible fraction	0.23	Living room	16h-22h

Internal heat gains			
<i>Occupation</i>			
Heat produced per person		Occupancy pattern	
Bedrooms	81 W	Bedrooms	22h-8h
Living room	108 W	Living room	14h-18h (50%)
Radiant fraction	0.30		18h-22h (100%)
<i>Electrical equipment</i>			
Living room	120 W	Occupancy pattern	
Radiant fraction	0.30	Living room	14h-22h
Windows and doors			
Status	Closed	Air infiltration	1 ren/h
Setpoint temperatures			
Cooling setpoint	25°C		1 ren/h
Heating setpoint	-		

Naturally, regions with different climates will have varying electricity consumption and savings with air conditioning. Therefore, houses were simulated in the different Brazilian Bioclimatic Zones (BZ). Brazil has 8 BZ, which group large areas with similar climates. As the regions covered by these zones do not perfectly align with the political divisions of states, an adaptation was necessary to assign each state to only one BZ. This adjustment was needed because we only have the number of buildings per state. The adaptation was based on each state's population density map, meaning the BZ of the region with the highest population density within the state was assumed for the entire state. Figure 3 illustrates the official and adapted division of bioclimatic zones, along with the cities simulated to represent each zone.

Figure 3 – Brazilian Bioclimatic Zones. Left: official classification by Brazilian Standard ABNT 15220. Right: adapted classification – 1 zone per state – according to the populational density of each state.

Table 4 presents the calculation of the final weighted average for the reduction in electricity consumption for internal conditioning in Brazil, amounting to 5.4%. Residential units were distributed proportionally to each state's population in 2011 (a necessary simplification due to the lack of available official data). Some states did not experience an improvement in energy consumption with the use of the new system, primarily due to climatic specificities. In such cases, the reduction was considered as 0%. This weighted average provides an overall assessment of the impact of the new system at the national level.

Table 4 – Energy consumption and energy savings from the conventional and new construction systems, for the adapted bioclimatic zones, according to the population of each state.

Brazilian State	Bio-climatic Zone (BZ)	Population (2011)	Number of housing units	Thermal load with conventional construction (kWh/year)	Thermal load with new materials (kWh/year)	% Reduction
Amazonas	BZ8	3,538,387	5,327	8,628	7,877	8.70%
Acre		746,386	1,124			8.70%
Rorãima		460,165	693			8.70%
Rondônia		1,576,455	2,373			8.70%
Amapá		684,309	1,030			8.70%
Pará		7,688,593	11,574			8.70%
Maranhão		6,645,761	10,004			8.70%
Piauí		3,140,328	4,727			8.70%
Ceará		8,530,155	12,841			8.70%
Rio Grande do Norte		3,198,657	4,815			8.70%
Paraíba		3,791,315	5,707			8.70%
Pernambuco		8,864,906	13,345			8.70%
Alagoas		3,143,384	4,732			8.70%
Sergipe		2,089,819	3,146			8.70%
Bahia		14,097,534	21,222			8.70%
Espírito Santo	3,547,055	5,340	8.70%			
Mato Grosso	BZ7	3,075,936	4,630	3,057	2,406	21.30%
Tocantins		1,400,892	2,109			21.30%
Goiás	BZ6	8,690,714	13,083	1,429	1,018	28.76%
Mato Grosso do Sul		2,477,542	3,730			28.76%
Minas Gerais	BZ3	19,728,701	29,699	No reduction	No reduction	0%
São Paulo		41,587,182	62,604			0%
Rio de Janeiro		16,112,678	24,255			0%
Santa Catarina		6,317,054	9,509			0%

Brazilian State	Bio-climatic Zone (BZ)	Population (2011)	Number of housing units	Thermal load with conventional construction (kWh/year)	Thermal load with new materials (kWh/year)	% Reduction
Paraná	BZ2	10,512,349	15,825			0%
Rio Grande do Sul		10,733,030	16,157			0%
Total:		192,379,287	289,600	Weighted average:		5.41%

7.2 Appendix II - Material inventories

In this appendix, the data used to calculate the altered materials inventory in the commodities of the SUTs is provided. Table 5 displays the total area of internal and external walls calculated from the model shown in Figure 2 for all houses constructed in 2011. Table 6 outlines the inputs used to construct 1m² of structural masonry walls. In the input calculations, we considered 1 layer of blocks covered by 2 layers of mortar (one on each side). Lastly, Table 7 details the inputs used to build 1m² of steel frame walls with drywall. To account for both sides of the wall, 2m² of drywall were considered for every 1m² of internal wall. For external walls, 1m² of drywall for the internal side and 1m² of cement board for the external side were taken into account.

As some of these inputs are industrialized, such as drywall panels, concrete blocks, and glass wool, the basic commodities used to produce them were sourced from open Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) databases, such as the European Platform on LCA (EPLCA) and the Brazilian Construction Environmental Performance Information System (Sidac). Resources that contributed to a total of less than 1 tonne for both internal and external walls were excluded from the analysis. This exclusion criterion was applied to streamline the assessment and focus on significant contributors to the overall material inventory.

Table 5 - Data from the low-income house model

	1 unit	289600 units
Floor área (m ²)	42	12163200
Total area of external walls (m ²)	70	20272000
Total area of internal walls (m ²)	51	14769600

Table 6 – Unit rate for the materials of the masonry wall (conventional construction).
Source: (PINI, 2008)

Structural masonry with concrete blocks, 10 mm joints with mixed mortar of cement, air lime and sand without sifting 1:0,25:3 - unit: m ² (TCPO code 04222.8.1)			Plaster (coating) for external wall with mixed mortar of cement, air lime and sand without sifting, mix 1:2:6, e = 20 mm - unit: m ² (TCPO code 09705.8.2.21)		
Construction Worker (experienced)	h	0.8000	Construction Worker (experienced)	h	0.8200
Construction Worker (non-experienced)	h	0.9340	Construction Worker (non-experienced)	h	0.6600
Sand (medium size, washed)	m ³	0.0163	Sand (medium size, washed)	m ³	0.0305
Air lime (Hydrated lime) type CH III	kg	0.8174	Air lime (Hydrated lime) type CH III	kg	6.0750
Portland Cement type CP II-E-32	kg	6.5124	Portland Cement type CP II-E-32	kg	6.0750
Structural Concrete Block	un	12.9000			

Table 7 – Unit rate for the materials of the steel frame (new materials).
Source: (PINI, 2008)

Steel frame for internal wall, plasterboard closure, for dry environment - unit: m ² (TCPO code 05125.8.15)		
Assistant worker	h	0.1000
Framing worker	h	0.5000
Plasterboard panel - with recessed edges for dry locations (thickness: 12.5mm / length: 2.40m / width: 1.20 m)	m ²	1.0000
GN 25 screw, self-drilling and self-tapping with trumpet head and needle point for plasterboard (length: 25 mm / diameter: 3.5 mm)	un	30.0000
Powder putty for treating joints in plasterboard sheets	kg	0.8700
U type profile, galvanized steel guide for steel frame (upright width: 90 mm)	m	0.8000
Type "C" profile, upright, in galvanized steel for steel frame (upright width: 90 mm)	m	2.7500
Microperforated paper tape for treating plasterboard joints (tape width: 50 mm)	m	3.0000
Self-adhesive resin-based soundproofing tape for plasterboard walls (tape width: 90 mm)	m	1.8300
Parabolt anchor, with hex nut (length: 95.2 mm /diameter: 3/8")	un	2.0300
Impact drill, electric, power. 0.9 HP (0.65 kW), chuck diameter: 5/8" - service life: 10,000 h	h prod.	0.1000
Glass wool, 5mm, roll	m ²	1.0000

